

Ancient Alien Architect Hypothesis and EPEMC (Brief)

A short discussion of Sitchinesque hypotheses and their theoretical placement
and/or congruence in Extended PEMC

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ABSTRACT

Many members of the alternative research community tout the plausibility of the Ancient Alien Architect Hypotheses, but do they conform to Electro-plasma cosmologies? Can they fulfill the requirements to become a portion of the Extension section of EPEMC? In this paper the author compares and contrasts mainstream, public, EPEMC, and Sitchinesque hypotheses looking for compatibility and contrasts. In some cases overlap is found, but in most cases the EPEMC simplicity supersedes the AAA hypotheses. However, there are some remaining holes in mainstream cosmologies which leave the public scratching their head, which creates gaps in human knowledge that seem to be more easily filled with religion, or ever increasingly: aliens. As the general movement of mankind is towards a scientific paradigm and away from the Religious Period, can a brave but outlandish pseudoscience like alien research find its footing in human mytho-historical context and defend itself? The author presents a final list of challenges to overcome for this to happen and for AAA to be accepted into EPEMC.

Key words: aliens - Atlantis - Genesis - Atrahasis - Enuma Elish - Sitchin - Nibiru - Planet X - Nine

Query

Simply put: can the hypothesis that ancient alien visitor-gods (that had human features) came to Earth, and mated with early hominids to create the human race, in two separate mixings, be viable in the EPEMC? Furthermore, does EPEMC standard cosmological profile of planet-gods and demigods (plus the constellations and stars), nullify these ideas? This would be the Saturnian, Jovian, Venetian and Martian hypotheses¹. See Table 1 below.

Table 1 :: EPEMC vs. Ancient Alien Hypothesis

	Mainstream ²	Public ³	EPEMC	Sitchianism
Creator God	EI/Ra/Osiris	Elohim	Kronos (Saturn)	Enki (Ea) ⁴
Destroyer God	YHWH/Set	Jehovah	Zeus (Jupiter)	Enlil
Heaven	Cosmos	The Kingdom	Sky after Saturn de-charge	Nibiru
Eden	Mythical place	Garden of life	Tepe Period	EDIN/space base
Elohim/Nephilim/Ann unaki	Angels Lit: limbs of EI	giants	Moons of Saturn and later Jupiter	Angel-messengers of Enki/Enlil Igigi ⁵
Adam and Eve	Mankind and Life	Literal first man and wife	open	Adamu= first breeding sire of mankind Eve=daughters of Ninurta

¹ See: Saturn Myth>>

“Worlds in Collision,” I Velikovsky, 1950

“The Saturn Myth”, D Talbott, 1985

Graph of Gods: <http://bit.ly/2BoN0hk>

[2] Table 2, pp. 5-7

Thunderbolts of the Gods <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5AUA7XS0TvA>

Symbols of an Alien Sky <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t7EAITcZFWY>

Remember the End of the World <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oophJNIP-fk>

“God Star,” D Cardona, 2005

Saturn and Purple Dawn Cosmology, G Jay <https://youtu.be/8XCpXpjV3MA> & <https://youtu.be/J6LMrgWyoWw>

² Archaeology and/or theology, anthropology; textual translations are most mainstream.

³ Much of this table is built on assumptions; this column is almost 100% built on it.

⁴ The union of these is Anu (Father-sky) or Ooranus

⁵ The role of the Igigi in coming “down” and mating with Adamu women in Africa appears to be some kind of explanation for black vs. light skinned men. Sitchin is not overt as far as I can tell, but the narrative surrounding Africa/Egypt vs Mesopotamia seems to make it clear what is meant. It’s a fascinating way of explaining the many cultural and genetic differences between Africa-Australians and Indo-european and Mongoloid peoples. However, people movement may also account for these differences. So it is not clear that such a hypothesis is necessary. Is Africa’s tendency to serve as a slave origin (multiple Biblical references), and the science that demonstrates ambition vs. instant gratification “issues” prevalent in African populations an indicator of cultural issues or genetic designed purpose? Why is Africa still so poor? Are they “destined” to serve lords? The author hopes not. For once, foreign powers need to leave Africa alone to grow and flourish with all of their wealth and potential! <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3463755/>
<https://www.tremr.com/Duck-Rabbit/african-americans-possess-violence-gene-researchers-find>
<https://vdare.com/articles/solving-the-african-iq-conundrum-winning-personality-masks-low-scores>
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0191886912000840>

War of the gods	Mythical, did not happen	Pagan stuff or battle of angels and demons	Vanir/Aesir clash symbolizes Jupiter stealing half the moons of Saturn, and collisions	Literally a nuclear holocaust caused by Marduk's quest for the throne and fighting with Enlil's sons; Yahweh becomes one of these sons
Creation of Man	Darwinian evolution	Or Genesis and other human origin stories/myths such as the Rig Veda, Pangu Myth, Greek legends, etc...	Mankind evolves along expanded civilization track, with inspiration from pantheon above and EMF/PEMS influence over religion and technology	Literally 1) Enki breeds with homo erectus 2) Ninurta breeds with them 3) Enki breeds with the daughters of Ninurta 4) Adamu's ribs used to mix DNA in ancient laboratory and create modern mankind 5) Igigi and Annunaki breed with humans as well
Satan	Seth	Lucifer ⁶	The Sun or Venus ⁷	Marduk / Nibiru

In order to address this it would require a much lengthier analysis. However, for now this *Brief* must suffice to answer the query so that other researchers utilizing EPEMC will know how to proceed with this “extension” issue. On the surface it is not much different than the addressing of Creationist Cosmology (Young Earth) and the Bible in EPEMC. However, the situation is now much more complicated by the fact that recent groundbreaking research by Mauro Biglino⁸ has revealed the pressing need to revisit the Bible from a non-theological perspective⁹, in the light that academia and public have been exposed to different translations of source texts.¹⁰

Compare & Contrast Compatibilities

Looking at Table 1, which is by no means complete, already major philosophical and theological - what could be termed pathogenic - fractures have appeared. Almost complete discordance and disagreement between not only the mainstream academic and public views, but also the Sitchian and PEMC views. So as it pertains to our query, the answer is a tactical “no.” The main crux of the issue is that the meaning and origin of the texts are basically diametrically opposing. While the Sitchian hypotheses tend towards mullyfing and

⁶ Ba'al, Beelzebub, ie Jupiter; matches the Marduk = Jupiter mainstream Sumerology

⁷ Venus being the Morning Star, as well as the cause of major catastrophe makes it very difficult to tell which body pulled apart Saturn's system (Osiris). According to Mayan myth the Venetian comet arose straight out of Saturn (but the Greeks say it was Jupiter), and this act was basically rebellious. But in Egyptian myth, Isis stitches Osiris back together, has sex with his dead body to conceive Horus, the one-eyed god (Zeus/Odin). This may be the most reliable, but the question remains is Isis Saturn or Venus? It may seem trivial, but in fact Saturn was frequently a man-woman. For example after Kronos' fall (for he was bound in rings), the four gods were Zeus, Hera, Poseidon, and Hades. Hera was Saturn, for Heracles is Ares is Mars. Mars and Earth have the same basic tilt as Saturn, and thus we know that they are related. As for Hades and Poseidon, those two gas giants were banished far out, and indeed they are too far away to see without telescope. Thus we know that once upon a time, they were not. Once upon a time they were listed as among the first. In Nordic culture they seem to have been part of the Vanir. Not lesser than Aesir, just different.

⁸ “The Book That Will Forever Change Our Ideas about the Bible,” M Biglino, 2013

⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9bFHAQM8aPk>

¹⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zFG_Kr3Mopg

modifying religious/theological hypotheses about important questions such as “why are we here?” and “who made us?” EPEMC remains firmly in league with the scientific and academic community, and rooted in the Scientific Period. It’s why, also, Flat Earth cannot be accepted in any shape or form (not even 11th dimensional “branes”) into EPEMC. HEGEME theory is alternative but firmly rooted in an interest in chemistry and physical geology-active, living geology. The hollowness is not actually hollow at all, but liquid¹¹. It’s a modification hypothesis that accepts the possibility that the Earth’s core is not molten iron/nickel, but some type of highly viscous metallic fluid, possibly a type of water or metallic hydrogen, acting as a sort of thermonuclear reactor via cosmic ray capture (Electrothermal Vine hypothesis¹²). But it’s certainly not an attempt to return to Ptolemaic or pseudo-Ptolemaic ideas.

It is certain that many mainstream academia would love to lump PEMC/EU™ theorists with flat earth, and aliens, etc... however it just isn’t so¹³. Need we remind the reader that EPEMC (Plasma Cosmology) is official since 1927, the same year as Big Bang, and has the same roots as Quantum and Relativity, going back as far as 1900-1905.¹⁴

However, for the sake of argument (to play the Devil’s Advocate, so to speak) let us say that there *is* a way to extend PEMC to contain literal ancient architects. What would that look like?

It would most certainly contain very heroic stories, but they would (the author imagines) be incredibly different in form. For starters, one of the most heavily harped-on critiques of Sitchian/von Daniken hypotheses is that the aliens they purport rely heavily upon stone age technology. It could be argued most of it was destroyed, washed away in the Flood(s), taken back to space, or just plain denied to the humans. However, the fact remains that we at this present time, appear more advanced (if not genetically, then in technology) than our alleged “creators.” If, for example Enki was a scientist engaging in nucleic recombination, why did he not use more sophisticated means, or have a more sophisticated lab? Or was such knowledge contained on the mysterious “ME”’s? Either way, the fact remains that this very day we know what DNA cloning and genetic engineering, of the kind of specificity Sitchin imagined, requires: very complex scientific equipment and super computers. The map of the human genome took nearly 20 years to complete. There is no mention of such an involved process in the Book of Enki, for example, where his methods are described.

The author will later explain what he thinks is the solution to the conundrum of “alien” gods (anthropogenic gods). For now, suffice it to say the entire proposal remains extremely dubious.

And yet... the fact remains that there are several holes and other questionable issues within mainstream biology¹⁵ and EPEMC biology, that require some further research or explanation¹⁶. Things which not even religion can cure, but only Sitchian hypothesis, et al...

1. Human rib-cage shape (vs other apes)¹⁷
2. Human throat (vs all other mammals)
3. Origins of human ideas, such as gods, weapons (especially swords¹⁸)
4. Strange human obsessions and general species direction/trajectory (see Figure 1)
5. Human linguistics
6. Human thumbs (vs all other animals)
7. Human brain changes¹⁹/skull size²⁰
8. Human arm:leg:torso ratio

¹¹ [4]

¹² [3]

¹³ [10]

¹⁴ [9] Table 1, pp. 2-3

¹⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=59z85GVkElw>

¹⁶ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2464272/>

¹⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8RnPwtHrNbQ>

¹⁸ [8]

¹⁹ <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2013/oct/17/skull-homo-erectus-human-evolution>

²⁰ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2018/05/180524141534.htm>

These are simply some of the peculiarities about the human form and development which have no general understanding in the other columns of Table 1, but are covered in exquisitely fine details in Sitchin's [questionable] but consistent (in most ways) translations of lost Sumerian texts.

Figure 1: Symbolic graph of animal vs. human evolution/trajectory

The tendency of humans to create things not found in the natural world (not simply a tool that is actually a stick or stone), is completely unusual, and at this time not explained in EPEMC. A vague idea exists in the alternative psychological studies about drugs, and if drugs were combined with electrical shapes in the sky, perhaps hallucinations could be the source of new knowledge? The author admits this is *not* supportable with EPEMC because it is *not* the simplest explanation when there are translations of Sumerian texts with straightforward answers. Occam's Razor would be to trust the cuneiform texts on clay.

Humans are industrious because they were designed to be workers, or at least slaves. Our obsession with gold was literally bred into us by masters who need it. All the wars of the Middle East are continued political battles of human overlords who have a dreaded family feud. The planets are named for kings and queens. Kingship was taught to mankind, and classism, racism, etc... were forced (as a "gift") upon our species. When we displeased them, or they made war, whole cities were destroyed or allowed to be destroyed.

It all sounds preposterous until you consider Planet Nine.²¹

Planet Nine (Planet X)

Nibir(u) is a factual translation²², and is not a Sitchin invention, nor unique to Sitchinesque hypotheses. In fact, the discussions of the "Black God" extend to MesoAmerica²³. What is unique to Sitchin's hypothesis is that the planet, which we will call Planet X, is described so vividly as a black sky planet, several times the size of Earth, with its own inner heat and a dying atmosphere.

²¹ So called due to diminution of Pluto, though it did turn out to be a planet.

<https://www.newscientist.com/article/mg20327181-600-is-pluto-a-planet-after-all/>

²² Enuma Elish, Fifth Tablet, <http://www.sacred-texts.com/ane/enuma.htm>

²³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tezcatlipoca>

Whence comes mankind's (leadership's) interest and obsession with geoengineering and climate change? Climate change has been an Earth fact throughout its entire existence, and throughout human history. Not only was Earth much hotter in the past, it was much hotter in human history. It was also much colder. The wild swings of our climate hardly necessitate an obsession with particulates in the air, particularly metals. So there is one odd thing about modern human behavior which bears questioning: what does spraying metals into the air have to do with carbon (which itself has little direct thermal impact on the planet²⁴, but only through forest cycles in the northern hemisphere)? The answer, when really observed, is: nothing.

While the EPEMC and author have little to conclude, and dare not, at this time, assert the obsession with geoengineering is direct evidence that Nibiruan leaders are influencing human science for their own ends (given there isn't any direct proof they are "out there" and have visited us), the author does assert that this is a strange road to travel, and when you go down it, it makes less sense than the hole leading to Alice's Wonderland. It is not even to be expected through the Looking Glass, because, after all, nothing of the sort is in natural behavior. Animals simply show no interest in modifying atmosphere. Redwood trees modify atmospheric humidity on "purpose" but that is a clear product of long term advanced evolution. But why should a new ape, with all the advantages of the planet's resources, imagination, and opposable thumbs seek to imbalance the environment and lead itself towards an extinction event? For trauma? Nothing in EPEMC/EU catastrophism and Velikovskianism (essentially abuse relationship with the gods) has any real bearing on this phenomenon!

The mainstream might argue that all sorts of human behaviors, such as technology, bootstrap themselves, building and building upon each other til nothing we do really reflects humanity seeking homeostasis. To which one must reply that *some* humans do seek homeostasis. We call them, "aborigines". They eschew civilization and do not think in modern paradigms. Some tribes have, of course, adapted and adopted. But even in the United States where this was more or less forced, tribalism and tribal values remains strong and generally politically in opposition to bureaucratic forces. Is this difference genetic? Is the story of Cain and Abel more than a metaphor for civilization and aboriginal/herders as Daniel Quinn asserted? Is it perhaps genetic, and related to the descendents of the line of Adam(u)?

Whatever the case may be there, the story of Nibiruans seeking gold to alter their atmosphere is intriguing in comparison to the modern post-Sitchin (d. 2010) and especially post publication event facts of geoengineering plans.

What's more, could he have been anymore (more or less) "on the money" about the research regarding Planet Nine? This "new" hypothesis²⁵ has made it more or less impossible to deny²⁶, as there are now known kuiper belt objects²⁷ moving in ways that defy gravity otherwise.²⁸

What are we to make of this *interesting* if not outright impossible correlation? From an EPEMC conservative perspective, actually it is quite easy to deal with. In the first place the Sumerians and Babylonians were excellent astronomers. Moreover, remember, that the solar system was quite different. The existence of a highly elliptical object, possibly even vertical based upon tablets, is not at all unpredicted or surprising. It is in fact the primary reason we expect Uranus is tilted to nearly vertical (98°). The texts record a close passage to the Saturnian and Jovian system. It is expected that this may have been what ended the typical dual-dual²⁹ solar system we already had, if not the approach of the sun as stated in the conclusion of the author's landmark work, "Plasma Petroglyphs (Plasmaglyphs), Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction."³⁰ In fact,

²⁴ "Climate Change: Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide. The global average atmospheric carbon dioxide in 2017 was 405.0 parts per million (ppm for short), with a range of uncertainty of plus or minus 0.1 ppm" or ~ 0.04%

<https://www.climate.gov/news-features/understanding-climate/climate-change-atmospheric-carbon-dioxide>

²⁵ <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/news.php?release=2017-259>

²⁶ <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/planets/hypothetical-planet-x/in-depth/>

²⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1809.02571.pdf>

²⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.05355.pdf>

²⁹ Saturn-Jupiter (Aesirs) orbiting the Sun (Apollo/Sol)

³⁰ [8], pp.132-136

this may alleviate the author from the difficult proposition of having to explain how Ra (Helios) was warm enough to spark life on Earth. Essentially it would be thus:

1. The Saturnian (coplanar to collinear)³¹ and later Jovian+Saturnian (non collinear conjunction) would be in the habitable zone. Hence the idea of Zeus (and Hera) sparking by “tossing stones over his back”.
2. The passage of the object “rips” out the “heart” of Quetzalcoatl³², hence the intrigue for the Mayans and Aztecs with the “Black God”
3. This ends the typical arrangement. Jupiter controls a few planets and steals Saturn’s moons³³.
4. It also causes (as the Enuma Elish says) the Great Flood
5. The system breaks down further and the rocky planets of Mercury, Earth, Venus, and Mars are flung towards the sun, but voltages and momentum help them find new orbits
6. Venus ceases to be a “Great Comet”
7. The passage of Planet X causes massive tilt of Uranus, slingshot of Neptune and especially Pluto and Triton

Supposedly the approach of Nibiru would be known beforehand as the planet is large (10x mass to Earth, minimum) and the entire Solar System Circuit (SSC) behavior alters as it comes and goes. This is all highly speculative and needs a means of testing either via very reliable simulation or laboratory testing. Though the electric currents in space are by now well established, it remains to be seen how to deal with them more specifically with regards to X and a changing circuitry. Does the arrival of “heralds” in the form of alien asteroids^{34 35 36} signal the approach of a black body planet³⁷? Possibly, but we do not yet know.

Here’s what strange phenomenon we do know is happening more and more:³⁸

1. Strange Red^{39 40 41} and Purple Skies^{42 43}
2. Trumpeting and horn sounds bellowing from the Earth^{44 45}
3. Increasing frequency of pilot reported UFO^{46 47}

Again, religion expects us to believe it is revelation, as such events are “Biblical” (literally *in the Bible*). Sitchin would say that these may presage the approach of Nibiru/X itself. But EPEMC merely states that we do not know, but it does seem to confirm a change in the SSC^{48 49}. Which happens to coincide with Grand

³¹ Ibid.

³² <http://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html>

³³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1809.00700.pdf>

³⁴ <http://www.ras.org.uk/news-and-press/3126-first-interstellar-immigrant-discovered-in-the-solar-system>

³⁵ <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/05/21/science/asteroid-interstellar-jupiter.html>

³⁶ <https://www.express.co.uk/news/science/1044761/asteroid-oumuamua-alien-cigar-asteroid-theory-extraterrestrial-harvard-university>

³⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.05334.pdf>

³⁸ Used to be Ball Lightning was weird. Now it is so common and large, governments are admitting to UFOs

³⁹ <https://www.livescience.com/61120-massive-geomagnetic-storm-discovered-from-1770.html>

⁴⁰ <http://science.sciencemag.org/content/ns-3/52/121>

⁴¹

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/peoplesdaily/article-3042260/Red-sky-morning-Chinese-city-fears-Armageddon-sky-turn-s-bright-red-rained-MUD.html>

⁴² <https://interestingengineering.com/the-reason-behind-the-purple-skies-that-appeared-after-hurricane-michael>

⁴³ <https://jasperandsardine.wordpress.com/2018/10/17/purple-skies-seen-again-in-ohio-and-florida/>

⁴⁴ <http://seektress.com/ssounds.htm>

⁴⁵ <http://thehum.info/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2017/dec/17/pentagon-admits-running-secret-ufo-investigation-for-five-years>

⁴⁷ <https://www.cnn.com/travel/article/ireland-ufo-pilots-intl/index.html>

⁴⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1807.11558.pdf>

⁴⁹ [4]

Solar Minimum⁵⁰, and with the changing position of the SSC around the Milky Way⁵¹, decreasing blocked cosmic rays and thereby theoretically increasing GEC effects upon Earth and other planets⁵². Essentially, there are new pressures. This may not coincide with X at all. The discovery of new cosmic rays may be telling, or not.⁵³

The Viracochan Hypotheses

In this discussion, there is also the Atlantean and Tepe Period diffusion issue to discuss. Chiefly, whether or not there were:

- ❑ Atlantean sea-faring colonizers who acted as Viracocha/Quetzalcoatl “civilizers”
 - ❑ Or were the Olmec Shang Chinese?⁵⁴
- ❑ Whether Atlanteans were Africans (specifically Mauritians)⁵⁵
- ❑ Whether or not Atlanteans found Gobekli Tepe
- ❑ Whether or not the “Lost Ten Tribes” were Viracochans
 - ❑ Or was it Phoenicians?
 - ❑ Or Sundaland peoples?⁵⁶
- ❑ Did Amazonians escape the Deluge to the north?⁵⁷
 - ❑ Or found the Mayans?
- ❑ Were these potential colonizers Egyptians?
 - ❑ Did they have small, hand-held electric devices to power tools?⁵⁸
- ❑ Are all of the polygonal stoneworks around the world sharing the same Atlantean or Tepe period signatures?
- ❑ Did stonework diffuse as well, so that perhaps the same ideas were just carried forth with fishermen?
- ❑ Were the Khumric (Welsh-Celtic) peoples Cimmerians and Trojans?⁵⁹

The plethora of possibilities available in the Viracochan hypotheses makes this a very difficult distillation in comparison not only with EPEMC (which all of the above can fit into), but also with Sitchin hypothesis (which is both aided by the above and yet harmed, via conflation and distortion.)

How is it conflated? Well, not to be too blunt but why would alien colonizers need to come from the sea, or walk, or carry power boxes? Why would they die or go back into the sea? If they are Atlanteans from the bottom of the ocean they certainly wouldn't need to be aliens from X. And if they are aliens from X that decide to go into the Earth (as giants supposedly did), then why would they do that, or be interested in humanity at all? The problems with combining our understanding of the advanced nature of aliens with discussions of giants or dwarves/faeries that live under hill is that there is a massive gap in plausibility and utility. The very logistics are threatened. In some faery stories they are super advanced surgeons and powerful alien-like beings, and in others ghastly, grotesque and dying. In all cases their technology always matches the era. So from carts to carriages to cars to planes to flying saucers... it is quite obviously psycho-cultural.⁶⁰

⁵⁰ <https://youtu.be/RoV97zCtJwk>

⁵¹ <https://sites.google.com/site/electricuniversegateway/recent-news/wherearewesolarsystemgoing-bendavidson>

⁵² By literally shrinking the heliopause or otherwise passing through; <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.02322.pdf>

⁵³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.00439.pdf>

⁵⁴ “Origin of the Olmec Civilization,” Xu, 1996

⁵⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U5kEzxOb-3c>

⁵⁶ <https://www.breakingisraelnews.com/77499/native-americans-part-ten-lost-tribes/>

⁵⁷ [3]

⁵⁸ So called “hand-bag phenomenon” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kvdrkSUVn70>

⁵⁹ “The Holy Kingdom,” A Gilbert, 1998

⁶⁰ “Supernatural,” G Hancock, 2005

And what would underground peoples have to do with giants who wear mermaid suits? Even in the Sumerian texts, are we seeing strange space-suits and spacecraft or are we seeing symbology messaging and fantasy? Is it not all too easy to take what they have said over literally? From the EPEMC perspective, the answer is yes.

Atlantean Period Ambiguities

As regards the Atlantis hypothesis, the author has a longer treatise which will be followed up by a close examination of the four best candidates (1) Azores, (2) Frisland, (3) Richat, and (4) South Spain. What must be discussed here is merely the aspect of the ambiguity of the level of technology of Atlantean period peoples. The author maintains that the answer lies squarely in Giza, which is demonstrably from the Atlantean and Tepe period. What we see there is a flourishing of technology from confirmed electrical power⁶¹, chemistry, and advanced stonework which includes alloys containing Ruthenium. We see advanced hydrology⁶² and plasma physics embedded into the Great Pyramid⁶³, as well as constellation alignments^{64 65} and monumental architecture.⁶⁶

What we do not see is computers, power lines, automobiles, or other signs of an immortally advanced culture. The crux is thus:

- The people of that period achieved their advancement as the result of steady cultural advancement, trade, and exploration, in awe and reverence of the splendor of the One God - Helios/Kronos/Ra/Shang Di/Brahma/Quetzalcoatl, from about 30-50 kya till the Younger Dryas catastrophe.^{67 68}
- Or the site is truly a monument to the gods, specifically Enki (for Africa was to belong to him and his progeny)⁶⁹; and the temples acted as a power station for advanced spacefare.
 - ◆ That Giza was a de facto space station/base for communication to Mars⁷⁰ and eventually Nibiru. A way to transport Gold out of Africa (via the Nile). Gold which was apparently taken from South Africa?⁷¹

Both of these seem far fetched to the mainstream, who have ignored mytho-historical data. They are not far fetched to the population, which for all its superstitiousness and gullibility, still know what seems realistic and what does not. The ramp-slave hypothesis of antiquated Victorian style Egyptology does not seem plausible at all. Logistics and most of the evidence simply does not support this.⁷² The ramp alone would need to be more of an engineering project than the pyramid!⁷³

Whatever the case may be on ancient technology, it does not seem likely that it was more advanced than we are now, except in specialized fields of knowledge. But most sound, heat, and other strange stone cutting techniques have actually been identified.⁷⁴ Where they haven't, mankind has figured out how to mold stone, which appears to have been the very method of construction at the Bosnian pyramids, which have a

⁶¹ "Giza Power Plant," C Dunn, 1998

⁶² http://sentinelkennels.com/Research_Article_V41.html

⁶³ <https://phys.org/news/2018-07-reveals-great-pyramid-giza-focus.html>

⁶⁴ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1109/1109.6266.pdf>

⁶⁵ [13] pp. 25-27

⁶⁶ "Lost Technologies of Ancient Egypt," C Dunn, 2010

⁶⁷ [2] Table 1 pp.2; Table 3 pp. 8

⁶⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rjrM1Saq9YU>

⁶⁹ "The 12th Planet," Z Sitchin, 1976

⁷⁰ Which was also destroyed not by Venus but by the nuclear war of the gods, conveniently.

⁷¹ For some reason ship up the coast but only to Kenya? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GkTj-NwLG0Y>

⁷² <https://www.cheops-pyramide.ch/khufu-pyramid/ramp-models.html>

⁷³ <https://www.cheops-pyramide.ch/khufu-pyramid/pyramid-theories.html>

⁷⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BsqOLCXYznE>

form of proto concrete.^{75 76} But this type of stone is very hard to prove that it is manmade. In fact, floatstone of all types can produce interesting results, as the author found out in an on site study at another location.⁷⁷

Sumerian Star Wars (and India)

There is an unpopular (with Sitchinites) hypothesis, that while it does not cover the list of anomalies presented above, does however explain the alien-god [double naming] conundrum. Chiefly, that the stories such as the Mahabharata, Enuma Elish, and Egyptian Book of the Dead describe not actual battles or religious practices even, but astronomical data in narrative form. In short: Star Wars for ancient peoples.

Take the Gilgamesh. It is a Heracleian story about a pseudo-king (much as Huangdi) demigod who appears to be human, but not only kills the “Bull of Heaven” (Taurus), but battles with Inanna/Ishtar (Venus) and wrestles a hideous monster, not unlike the gorgons of Greek myth or the monsters/Jotun of Nordic myth. He sets out to find everlasting life only to learn the gods get it from a plant, after he learns the truth about the Deluge. He loses the plant that gives everlasting life, not too unlike the way Adam (the Heaven-Man in EPEMC myth) loses Eden when he consumes from the Tree of Knowledge, except that Gilgamesh loses it to a sea serpent. Meanwhile, his Nordic counterpart, Thor defeats a sea-monster which will later return to destroy him in an epic battle.

Does this sound like alien gods? More like the battle of Mars with the Venetian comet-tail, which of course was a repeat of the epic battle Zeus/Jupiter had with Typhon when Jupiter crossed the comet tail earlier on. But while that battle appears to have been in the beginning of Marduk’s power, the former appears to be towards the zenith of the “war of the gods”. This is reflected in the fact that the Rig Veda precedes the Upanishads, which end with the extremely long Mahabharata, within which Dwaraka sinks. We can, therefore, by carbon dating Dwaraka, know when that occurred, and by this means find out when the solar system fell apart.

The author does not subscribe to the idea that the radioactive dust found at Harappa and Sodom are from nuclear war. The Seven Winds of Destruction are more likely to be different types of vortex winds:

1. Super tornadoes
2. Tai-fengs (hurricanes, etc...)⁷⁸
3. Micro to macrobursts
4. Mountain forming gales⁷⁹
5. Arc discharge concussions
6. Or explosive comets/meteors (such as Tunguska)⁸⁰
7. Volcanic explosions/Pyroclastic flows

So what are we to make of the gap in human development story? Probably that we simply do not have enough skeletons to fill the gap, or that we’ve underestimated the power of electricity in evolutionary processes. What if by sequestering positrons or nuclei, or causing fusion and fission, very high arc discharge also alters electromagnetic environments to push along mutations in mammalian DNA? Seems far fetched, but stranger things have happened. Therefore the EPEMC must not be quick to support the alien hypothesis, until further data reveals itself over time.

⁷⁵ <https://www.davidovits.info/the-pyramids-in-bosnia-europe-perhaps-in-roman-concrete/>

⁷⁶ <https://irna.fr/First-impressions-from-Robert.html?lang=en>

⁷⁷ https://www.academia.edu/37817203/Trip_Report_Culvertown_Platform_Formation

⁷⁸ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1029/2018SW001995>

⁷⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fDIRMB3hVQM>

⁸⁰ <https://www.sciencenews.org/article/exploding-meteor-may-have-wiped-out-ancient-dead-sea-communities>

Conclusions

Until Planet Nine/X reveals itself, physical evidence for the Ancient Alien Architect hypothesis appears to remain elusive, speculative, jostled, disjointed, internally contradictory, and wistful at best. However, because of gaps left open by mainstream biology and archaeology, as well as EPEMC (purposefully), there remains some viable hope that there are interesting and unique truths to discuss. While no evidence supports giant man-gods that can carry lions (and yet mate with human women), it does show a lot of support for the concept of mytho-historical astronomy which plays out as a form of narrative. The story of Quetzalcoatl is an excellent example, wherein the story of a king being killed suddenly becomes a third person narrative about a star⁸¹. It parallels closely many aspects of the Osiris myth which shares the same anthropomorphic treatment of astronomical data disguised both as narrative and religious rites or ritual. Later generations of Egyptians took these things literally, as did the Hindus, in the formation of worshipful religions. The Bible itself inherited a number of Sumero-Babylonian myths which contain both historical events (such as the Flood), and allegories (such as Noah-Ziusudra) and demonstrate astronomical evidence of solar system catastrophe (such as Enlil killing all of humanity because we were “noisy”⁸²).

Recent events have called into question the behaviors of our SSC, especially as we head towards GEC changes and Grand Solar Minimum. But it is too early to categorize all human behavior as related to the whims of secret overlord aliens (rather than billionaire humans). This hypothesis notwithstanding, it remains possible to have both concurrently, and the Sitchin hypothesis fills many gaps not covered by catastrophe-driven psychology, archetypes, and motifs. It also fills certain political, social, economic, and racial realities by describing difficult answers succinctly in the context of a nobility super-elite class warfare. The great charge against this being the ease with which it does so; but the greatest support for it being the vast amount of internally mostly consistent translation of actual texts. However, problems with alien hypotheses’ proponents’ translations are well known and vocally disputed.

In the end sum, EPEMC must remain aloof but interested; open to modification, especially as it relates to Planet X, and the possibilities of the black body rogue planet. Until that is proven, the author and EPEMC researchers are advised to consider Atlantis and Atlantean Period cultures as being related to normal human evolution, accelerated by technological breakthroughs, perhaps enhanced by study of the EMF/UAF (or our creation). Furthermore unknown gaps will be filled as time progresses and research improves, so long as X isn’t real and comes to destroy us all. In 150 years the discovery of electricity has totally revolutionized human living and our power over nature and the environment.

The author maintains that 30,000 or even 10,000 years unmolested by catastrophe could produce amazing cultures and civilizations that seem exotic and advanced. But none of them are as advanced as our culture, and it remains to be shown that alien overlords could have been more advanced. Until hard physical evidence emerges, the remainder must be regarded as pseudoscience or even *bunk* as the case may be.

⁸¹ Ibid.

⁸² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Enlil>

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